

Granting Accessible Tourism for Everyone – GATE

Report on the Accessibility Tools with Showcase Implementations

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1 Introduction and overview

1.1 Report purpose

This report documents the development of the GATE IT tools for accessible online content and the showcases for the tools. Formally the documentation concerns the work carried out by independent L. in work package 4 of the project.

The development of the tools was not aimed to create new tourism portals, but to provide existing websites with tools (software, modules or content templates) for data input, management, visualisation and access. The development builds on acknowledged good practices of “South Tyrol for all”.

One focus of the developed tools was to enable organisations easy provision of accessible multimedia content on natural and cultural heritage sites.

1.2 Focus on accessible multimedia content

Accessible online tools

A focus of the development of the IT tools has been multimedia content with the aim to enable the websites of the GATE pilot sites (project WP5), and of other organisations in the Interreg programme area, easy provision of accessible content on natural and cultural heritage sites.

Designed to be barrier-free, the developed tools (software, modules or content templates) fulfil the requirements of digital accessibility for all (i.e. W3C Web Content Accessibility Guidelines) and provide the user with information on the accessibility of sites or points of interest.

Features for users with disabilities include: barrier-free design, accessible navigation, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, capability for different languages (including sign language) and in-depth content on topics.

Collaboration

Project partner independent L. developed the GATE IT Tool for accessible points of interest and coordinated the realisation of the Chatbot and the Webapp for multimedia content. These two tools have been developed by the specialised software company U-Hooper (Trento).

The graphic concepts and the aspects of inclusive digital/Web accessibility have been realised in collaboration with a commissioned expert. The development of the showcases required close collaboration with staff of the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach. Curators of the Museum of Nature South Tyrol (Bolzano) supported the development of scientific content.

In the development of accessible multimedia content exchange of experience and integration of subject-specific skills in a wide range of areas is of decisive importance for a successful final product and valuable user information and experience. Challenges in the realisation of the GATE tools and showcases could be mastered thanks to the good cooperation of all participants.

Showcase implementations

In order to demonstrate the accessible online tools, independent L. worked out an implementation plan for the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach for the developed tools. This required close cooperation with the visitor centre of the GEOPARC Bletterbach. The centre can now update and expand the contents in the implemented tools at any time, i.e. further points of interest for

people with disabilities in the IT-Tool GATE, additional barrier-free theme paths in the Webapp, and also the Chatbot can be updated and expanded at any time. The implemented showcases can be replicated by the other GATE pilot sites as well as other interested sites in the Interreg programme area (and beyond).

1.3 The IT tools and showcases

Four tools have been created, three of which with a showcase implementation for the GEOPARC Bletterbach area:

- *IT-Tool for points of interest:* This is a plugin module for the most widely used Web-CMS WordPress that enables organisations to highlight on an online map (e.g. Open Street Map) points of interest in the area and provide structured information on the accessibility of the POIs. A showcase of this tool is implemented on the website of the GEOPARC Bletterbach visitor centre.¹

The program code for the plugin module, a digital form for data collection, and a manual (in English, German and Italian) with instructions for programming and data entry are provided free of charge from independent L.

- *Webapp for multimedia contents:* The Webapp enables organisations to provide users in a barrier-free way interactive contents for sites such as parks and hiking trails. The showcase for this application is the “GEOPARC Guide”² that explains the UNESCO World Heritage area and invites hikers on the Passo Oclini – Malga Gurndinalm trail to experience the landscape and nature. On the trail at eight points of interest QR-codes allow calling up content that promotes such experiences.

The developed content management system for the application is available for use by interested organisations, who can fill the programmed templates with digital content to create an audio guide for their own pilot site.

- *Chatbot for site information:* A chatbot enables an operator of a site to provide information about the site and available services automatically (e.g. opening hours, bus connections, guided tours, etc.). The developed showcase “Bletterbot” for the GEOPARC Bletterbach is implemented on the their Facebook page.³

The developed chatbot module for the Facebook messenger service is available for interested organisations from independent L.

- *Parking space finder for people with disabilities:* For the existing parking space finder app for South Tyrol⁴ a solution has been developed to display the occupancy status (“free/occupied”) of the parking spaces in real time. In the pilot measure, 10 parking spaces in Bolzano were equipped with an “in ground” parking space sensor.

For organisations interested to implement the solution in other regions information on the setup such as sensor, web services, etc. can be provided by independent L.

¹ GEOPARC Bletterbach: Interaktive Karte, <https://www.bletterbach.info/interaktive-karte>

² GEOPARC Guide: Webapp with more information, <https://guide.machineria.it/bletterbach/list>

³ GEOPARC Bletterbach: Bletterbot (under “Send Message”), <https://www.facebook.com/bletterbachvirtuell>

⁴ South Tyrol for all: Parking space finder, <https://www.altoadigepertutti.it/de/parkplatzfinder>

2 IT tools for accessible online information

2.1 Tool for accessible points of interest

This tool, generally referred to the IT-Tool GATE, offers interested organisations in the Interreg programme area (and beyond) the possibility to display on their website on a digital map points of interest (POI) in the surrounding of their location with useful information for people with disabilities.

Designed based on web accessibility standards, the application fulfils the requirements of digital accessibility for all, and provides users with structured information about the accessibility of points of interest. Programmed for the most widely used open source Web-CMS WordPress, the software code, a digital form for data entry, and a manual can be requested free of charge by interested organisations from independent L.

2.1.1 Tool development

The GATE IT tool was developed by the Webcentre of independent L. following good practices for inclusive tools of “South Tyrol for all”. The developers choose the open source Web-CMS WordPress that allows maximum adaptability of the module (plugin). With a worldwide market share of over 60 percent, WordPress is the most widely used Web-CMS, in comparison Joomla and Drupal have only market shares of 3 and 4.8 percent, respectively.

The conceptual and content design of the innovative GATE tool was developed by the internal project team in cooperation with an external graphic designer, with special attention to the aspects of digital/Web accessibility.

The visual representation of the tool is divided into two parts: Frontend – the part visible to the public, and backend – the part visible to the administrator of the web pages for data entry. The frontend view can be adapted graphically (e.g. colours) to fit with the design of the operator’s website.

The tool shows the inserted POIs in the vicinity of the organisation as georeferenced points on a digital map, OpenStreetMap with Layer Mapbox, or optionally on a list. When the user clicks on one of the set points on the map, a pop-up window opens with information about the selected POI: name and photo of the structure, contact details and various information on the accessibility of the POI (see below). Alternatively, the end user can view all data entries on a results list, with a button to display the respective point on the map.

2.1.2 Features for users with impairments

Technically the tools supports accessible map-based or list view, navigation of pages with structured information, adjustable font size, capability for information in different languages, text-to-speech function. The structured information includes: name and photo of the point of interest, accessibility description and rating with smileys, pictograms for different categories of impairment, information about services, characteristics, obstacles, orientation elements and comments.

2.1.3 Showcase implementation

The GATE IT Tool was programmed as an open source application and as an innovative instrument it is optimized for all potential user groups. As a showcase the plugin has been implemented on the

website of the visitor centre of the GEOPARC Bletterbach⁵, which is the GATE pilot site in South Tyrol. For this purpose, cooperation with the commissioned manager of the visitor centre's website was necessary.

The estimated informatics effort for the implementation of the tool in the WordPress based website was less than 4 work hours, which corresponds to estimated costs of about 350 Euros (plus legal VAT) according to the average remuneration tariff of a Web developer. For the implementation of the tool, a detailed, trilingual user documentation (manual for developers, user manual for data entry) is available.

2.1.4 Testing of the tool

Independent L. carried out a testing of the accessibility and usability of the programmed tool. At the beginning of March 2020, the beta version of the tool was sent to all GATE project partners and the pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach for testing in order to evaluate the informatics implementation and data management of the module (widget).

Before the official release, independent L. received a working copy of the entire website of the GEOPARC Bletterbach from their commissioned website programmer for the safe execution of the final informatics tests. In addition, the pilot site has been supported with the input of first points of interest into the implemented GATE IT Tool.

The Municipality of Santorso is interested to implement the tool in the Parco Rossi website to show its visitors accessible service facilities in the area. In a second step, the information could be extended to all of the municipal territory, for which the municipality is thinking of a possible cooperation with local stakeholders.

In this regard, it has been shown that a technical data entry form for the specific collection of data is needed that is identical to the input mask of the GATE IT Tool. For this reason, a corresponding technical data collection form was developed and included in the delivery package of the tool.

2.1.5 Launch of the application

Since September 2020 the final version of the GATE IT Tool is available together with detailed manuals in English, German and Italian. A product description of the tool has been published on the project website (<https://gateproject.dolomitiunesco.info>). The program code for the module and instructions for programming and data entry are provided free of charge to interested organisations throughout the Interreg programme area (and beyond) upon request writing to info@suedtirolfueralle.it (subject: GATE IT Tool).

2.1.6 Collection of user data and feedback

The operator of the website of the GEOPARC Bletterbach visitor centre can monitor the usage of the application at any time. In addition, a feedback question on the tool will be included in the visitor questionnaire of the GEOPARC Bletterbach, which the centre uses for quality assurance.

During the Corona crisis this year the GEOPARC Bletterbach opened, but with a much reduced number of staff. Therefore, it was not possible to provide services that are not absolutely necessary for the maintenance of operations. This also included the visitor survey, which is interrupted for the first time in about 10 years, because the handling of the questionnaires is time consuming, if not impossible at all, due to the necessary safety measures.

⁵ GEOPARC Bletterbach: Interaktive Karte, <https://www.bletterbach.info/interaktive-karte/>

2.1.7 Potential for organisations

The inclusive GATE IT Tool can be requested by interested organisations from independent L. Once implemented, entries with information about the accessibility of points of interest in the organisation's vicinity can be inserted in the tool, made available and updated at any time. In cooperation with other local stakeholders also accessible places in an entire city, nature park or other area can be covered with the tool.

2.1.8 The GATE IT Tool in brief

GATE IT Tool – Brief description

Independent L. has developed an innovative IT-tool based on the good practices of “South Tyrol for all”. The tool can be easily integrated as a module (plugin) into websites programmed with WordPress that is the most widely used Web-CMS. Particular attention has been paid to the digital/Web accessibility of the tool, which is tested thoroughly.

The tool allows operators of heritage, tourist or other facilities to display on their website on a map (e.g. Open Street Map) points of interest in the surrounding of the organisation, informing visitors about their accessibility. The front-end of the widget can be adapted graphically to the own website.

The GATE IT-tool is available free of charge to interested organisations in the Interreg programme area (and beyond). It can be requested via the e-mail address info@suedtirolfueralle.it (subject: GATE IT-Tool). Provided are the programme source code for the module, a manual (English, German, Italian) with instructions for programming, a form for data collection, and instructions for data entry.

2.2 Webapp for multimedia contents

This Webapp has been developed to enable the GATE pilot sites (and others) making available accessible multimedia contents for their websites and mobile applications. The Webapp has been realised by the software company U-Hopper (Trento) on behalf of the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, under the coordination of independent L.

A showcase implementation of the Webapp has been implemented for the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach. The GEOPARC Guide demonstrates the added value organisations can achieve with the Webapp in providing accessible multimedia contents for all. The showcase is particularly relevant for hiking trails that are among the most widely available nature experiences in the Alpine and pre-Alpine regions.

2.2.1 Webapp development

For the conceptual and content-related design of the Webapp, the commissioned software company U-Hopper facilitated workshops with representatives of the client Foundation Dolomites UNESCO and independent L., and curators of the GEOPARC Bletterbach and the Museum of Nature South Tyrol, who supported the application development regarding didactic, content-related and scientific aspects. The museum curators also represented the interests of end-user service organisations in the development.

Based on the collected inputs, U-Hopper developed the Webapp for multimedia contents with barrier-free web design. To support the use of the Webapp for hiking trails the concept of the application also includes information stations with QR-codes for multimedia delivery at points of interest. An expert in digital accessibility and usability reviewed the application.

2.2.2 Features for users with impairments

Features for users with disabilities include: barrier-free responsive Web design, easy to understand tutorial as an introduction to the Webapp, barrier-free page navigation, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, podcast audio content, capability to include content in different languages and in-depth content on topics. The showcase implementation is available in English, German, Italian and Italian Sign Language LIS.

2.2.3 Showcase implementation

The following detailed description of the showcase implementation is meant to provide guidance for organisations who wish to use a Webapp for inclusive communication with multimedia contents of a hiking trail. For the showcase Webapp GEOPARC Guide the accessible hiking trail from Passo Oclini to the Gurndinalm, a hike of about one hour, has been selected. This is a trail suitable also for families with a stroller and users of a motorised wheelchair (e.g. Swiss-Trac).

The trail is located above the Bletterbach Gorge. Tests conducted in advance in the gorge showed that the mobile phone network there does not guarantee sufficient data reception, and the pilot site did not want to allow distracting technical devices directly in the gorge, due to the risk of accidents. The GEOPARC Guide therefore aims to inform potential visitors on the Internet and day-trippers in the nearby hiking area Passo Oclini about the special features of the GEOPARC Bletterbach and hiking trail, thus encouraging them to visit the area.

Production plan

24 weeks were planned for the realisation of the Webapp and the showcase implementation Bletterbach Guide:

- Week 1: Project assignment and project start
- Weeks 2-3: Exchange with stakeholders
- Weeks 4-7: First prototype Webapp for multimedia contents
- Weeks 8-14: Definition and production of the contents of the Bletterbach Guide
- Weeks 15-17: Set up of an information panel and 8 information stations for points of interest with QR-codes on the trail
- Weeks 18-23: Final Webapp implementation and testing
- Week 24: Launch of the multimedia guide

Due to the early onset of winter in autumn 2019, which made the necessary image acquisition impossible, and the Coronavirus crisis from March 2020 the specified schedule could not be met.

2.2.4 Realisation and testing

The development team elaborated the overall concept for the showcase with the Webapp and multimedia contents based on barrier-free design. The core development team comprised of the software company U-Hopper, staff of the GEOPARC Bletterbach and museum curators as subject-experts, a content designer with expertise in accessible digital media, and experts of the project coordinator independent L. in physical and digital accessibility.

This setup was chosen to ensure that the planned application meets the interests of organisations and end-users. The testing of the Bletterbach Guide took place in plenary sessions, with the involvement of experts in Web accessibility and usability for people with disabilities. The extensive testing of the application in the field showed that only minor final adaptations were necessary in this regard. For example, the mandatory language selection after activation of the Webapp was supplemented by an automatic language selection via IP access.

The Webapp has been implemented in four languages (English, German, Italian, and Italian sign language for people with hearing disabilities), with content suitable for adults and children, barrier-free page navigation, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, and easy activation of the Webapp via QR-codes. A tutorial for the Webapp is also available. Along a didactic theme path from the Passo Oclini to the Gurndinalm eight information stations with QR-codes are installed. Furthermore a barrier-free board with information about the hiking trail and available Webapp is placed at the starting point of the footpath at the Passo Oclini car park.

The Bletterbach Guide includes information and a short video on the Bletterbach Gorge Virtual Reality application that is accessible in the GEOMuseum Redagno. The Guide is being promoted in the Bletterbach Chatbot (“Bletterbot”) and on the GATE project website.

2.2.5 Promoting experiences

The Webapp Bletterbach Guide has been launched for end-users on the 13th of October 2020. The entire themed hike from the Passo Oclini to the Gurndinalm with the guide takes about 1.5 hours. If users do not want to do the whole themed hike, they can still have the entire contents displayed in chronological order. Special emphasis was placed on an interest-based, multi-level information transfer to children and adults. Thus, the users can learn about certain topics in more or less depth. The application promotes an active experience of nature by inviting the users to look at the

surrounding or particular natural elements, and to engage with them, for example by consciously perceiving the landscape or feeling something with their hands.

2.2.6 Collection of user data and feedback

Data on the usage of the Webapp can be collected by means of digital user statistics. The GEOPARC Bletterbach Visitor Centre will fill in an evaluation form, describing how the application is integrated in the daily operation of the centre. A feedback question on the guide will be included in the visitor questionnaire of the GEOPARC Bletterbach that is being used for quality assurance.

During the Corona crisis this year the GEOPARC Bletterbach opened, but with a much reduced number of staff. Therefore, it was not possible to provide services that are not absolutely necessary for the maintenance of operations. This also included the visitor survey, which is interrupted for the first time in about 10 years, because the handling of the questionnaires is time consuming, if not impossible at all, due to the necessary safety measures.

2.2.7 Potential for organisations

The barrier-free Webapp for multimedia contents enables organisations to support an inclusive nature experience for everyone. The developed content management system for the application is available for use by interested organisations, who can fill the programmed templates with digital content to create an audio guide for their own pilot site. Particular attention has been paid to the replicability of the showcase implementation at other sites in the Interreg programme area. The showcase is particularly relevant for hiking trails that are among the most widely available nature experiences in the Alpine and pre-Alpine regions.

2.2.8 The Webapp in brief

Webapp for multimedia contents – brief description

The barrier-free Webapp for multimedia contents has been developed by the software company U-Hopper (Trento) on behalf of the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, under the coordination of independent L. The Webapp enables organisations to support an inclusive nature experience for everyone.

Noteworthy features of the tool are: Barrier-free responsive Web design, easy to understand tutorial as an introduction to the Webapp, barrier-free page navigation, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, podcast audio content, capability to include content in different languages and in-depth content on topics. The application can also be activated with QR-codes.

The developed content management system for the application is available for use by interested organisations, who can fill the programmed templates with digital content to create an audio guide for their own pilot site. The showcase implementation of the Webapp has been realised for the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach. The showcase is particularly relevant for hiking trails that are the most widely available nature experiences in the Alpine and pre-Alpine regions.

2.3 Chatbot for touristic site information

The chatbot for providing information about touristic sites has been developed by the specialised software company U-Hopper (Trento), on behalf of the UNESCO Dolomites Foundation, under the coordination of independent L. The chatbot application is based on the Facebook messenger service, and the developed module for this service is available free of charge for interested organisations from independent L.

A showcase implementation of the chatbot has been realised for the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach⁶ which demonstrates the added value organisations can achieve by providing information about available services at a natural or cultural heritage site to interested visitors automatically.

2.3.1 Tool development

The technology chosen for the innovative information service is the messenger service of Facebook, which has a large user community. What is less known is that the messenger service provides very good digital accessibility.

For the conceptual and content-related design, U-Hopper organised workshops with the project team, which included a software developer, an expert in narrative forms (storytelling), a specialist in digital accessibility, and the project coordinator. In the development of the showcase implementation also representatives of the GEOPARC Bletterbach and the South Tyrol Museum of Nature (Bolzano) participated. They represented the user perspective and supported the development of the didactic and content-related aspects of the information service (e.g. scientific content on geology and fossils).

The chatbot had to provide information about the site, in our case the GEOPARC Bletterbach, and useful information such as opening hours, guided tours, etc., and of course arouse interest to visit the site. On the basis of the elaborated concept, U-Hopper developed the chatbot module and implemented it on the Facebook page of the GEOPARC Bletterbach.

2.3.2 Features for users with impairments

Features for users with disabilities include: barrier-free navigation, user-friendly design of the pre-programmed chat flow, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, capability to include content in different languages. The showcase implementation is available in English, German and Italian. It includes also a promotional video about the virtual reality tour of the Bletterbach Gorge with Italian sign language (LIS) for people with hearing impairments. A game for children is also included in the chatbot.

2.3.3 Showcase implementation

The production plan foresaw 24 weeks for the realisation of the prototype and implementation of the showcase “Bletterbot” (Bletterbach Chatbot) application:

Week 1: Project assignment and project start

Weeks 2-3: Exchange with stakeholders

⁶ Bletterbot (under “Send Message”), <https://www.facebook.com/bletterbachvirtuell>

- Weeks 4-8: First prototype of the chatbot
Weeks 9-16: Definition and production of the “Bletterbot” contents
Weeks 17-23: Final test and implementation
Week 24: Launch of the “Bletterbot”

The originally set schedule for the realisation of the chatbot and the specific “Bletterbot” content could not be met due to the COVID-19 crisis.

2.3.4 Testing and launch of the tool

After extensive technical testing of the developed “Bletterbot” by U-Hopper, it was evaluated in plenary by the project team. The final version was published in September 2020 on the Facebook Page of the GEOPARC Bletterbach visitor centre.⁷

2.3.5 Interaction and user experience

A chatbot is a very useful tool for the operator of a touristic visitor centre to answer requests for service information automatically. The user starts the automated conversation and the chatbot responds with prepared information texts, provides audio recordings or videos, and information from connected databases.

The interaction setting developed for the Bletterbot is entertaining, yet informative and thus meets the institutional requirement. In comparison to providing information on the Facebook page, the developed chat enables a more natural conversation based on interests.

The chatbot menu allows all users to modulate the information offered in a very natural way. Special attention was placed on a multi-level information transfer to adults and children. The preferred format is storytelling, appealing rather than didactic. For some content, playful techniques (quiz, simulation) is being used, while for others a more reflective mode (e.g. natural history content).

Participants of an online workshop in November 2020 tried the application and expressed their enthusiasm about the intuitive communication design and details such as the integration of a game for children.

2.3.6 Collection of user data and feedback

Data on the usage of the messenger service based chatbot can be collected by means of digital user statistics and the number of followers. In addition, special analyses of the usage and interest of the users are possible. A feedback question on the chatbot will be included next year in the visitor questionnaire of the GEOPARC Bletterbach that is being used for quality assurance.

2.3.7 Potential for organisations

A chatbot is an ideal tool for operators of cultural and natural heritage sites (e.g. visitor centre) to provide information to interested visitors about the site and available services automatically (e.g. opening hours, bus connections, guided tours, etc.). The developed chatbot can be accessed from any Web-enabled device via Facebook and allows an engaging automated conversation for everyone, with and without impairments. The operator of the chatbot can update and extend the contents at

⁷ Bletterbot (under “Send Message”), <https://www.facebook.com/bletterbachvirtuell>

any time. Particular attention was paid to the replicability of the solution by pilot sites of GATE partners and other potential users.

The developed chatbot module for the Facebook messenger service is available for interested organisations free of charge from independent L. A tutorial for the chatbot is also available.

2.3.8 The Chatbot in brief

Chatbot for site information – brief description

The barrier-free chatbot has been developed by the software company U-Hopper (Trento) on behalf of the Foundation Dolomites UNESCO, under the coordination of independent L. A chatbot is an ideal tool for operators of cultural and natural heritage sites (e.g. visitor centre) to provide information to interested visitors about the site and available services automatically (e.g. opening hours, bus connections, guided tours, etc.).

The chatbot is implemented based on the messenger service of Facebook. In the automated interaction the chatbot can provide prepared information texts, audio recordings or videos, and information from connected databases. Features for users with disabilities include: barrier-free navigation, user-friendly design of the pre-programmed chat flow, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function, capability to include content in different languages. A showcase implementation of the chatbot has been realised for the South Tyrolean pilot site GEOPARC Bletterbach.

The developed chatbot module for the Facebook messenger service is available for interested organisations free of charge from independent L. A tutorial for the chatbot is also available.

2.4 Application for barrier-free mobility

An extension of the existing App parking space finder for people with disabilities of “South Tyrol for all” has been developed. The new function enables the application to display in real time the occupancy status (“free/occupied”) of reserved parking spaces. The solution requires the installation of “in ground” sensors which detect the presence or absence of a vehicle and transmit the data in real time to the database of the parking space finder.

In the pilot measure the web services for the application have been developed and 10 parking spaces equipped with a sensor to test and validate the setup. For organisations interested to implement the solution in other regions information on the setup such as sensor, web services, etc. can be provided by independent L.

2.4.1 Extension of a parking space finder

Independent L. has developed for “South Tyrol for all” a barrier-free car park finder for people with disabilities, which helps them to find reserved parking spaces. The car park finder has been published in 2016 on the website of “South Tyrol for all”⁸, since then downloaded over 10.000 times.

A province wide survey was conducted by independent L. and over 1.300 parking spaces reserved for people with disabilities have been geo-referenced with Mobile Mapper 100 in the 116 municipalities of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano - South Tyrol. To provide the parking space information in digital format, an intuitive app has been designed for people with disabilities, giving them the possibility to search and reach a suitable reserved parking space close to the chosen destination, using the navigation function of the smartphone. The application allows the operator to include new reserved parking spaces, modify the information about existing ones, and users to report any difficulties of access to other users.

Within the GATE project, an extension of the car park finder by the function “free/occupied” has been developed to enable the application display in real time the occupancy status of reserved parking spaces. In the pilot measure also 10 parking spaces in Bolzano have been equipped with an “in ground” sensor. The respective databases and digital interfaces (web services) have been developed by independent L., and the car park finder has been configured by the commissioned software company U-Hopper (Trento) to show the new function.

2.4.2 Features for users with impairments

App for iOS- and Android-based devices showing reserved car park spaces for disabled people extended by the function “free/occupied”; sensors and data transmission for the function implemented at 10 parking spaces in Bolzano; the app comes with an easy tutorial, notification function for users, accessible online navigation function, accessibility description, adjustable font size, text-to-speech function.

2.4.3 Implementation and testing

Regarding the required technology, the chosen “in ground” parking space sensor is based on a magnetic detection system that accurately detects the presence or absence of a vehicle at an equipped parking space. The sensor has an integrated LoRa communication system to communicate with LPWAN compatible gateways that are building up the Smart City network of Bolzano. The sensors have to provide continuously an energy-efficient vehicle detection (without missing a parking

⁸ South Tyrol for all: Parking space finder, <https://www.altoadigepertutti.it/de/parkplatzfinder>

or departure event), wireless configuration capabilities and software updates via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE).

In order to determine the parking positions for the pilot measure, independent L. drew up a priority list for possible locations in Bolzano, and the company commissioned to install the sensors checked all chosen positions on site for available signal strength (LoRaWAN). Then independent L. applied to the Municipality of Bolzano for permission to install 10 sensors at checked positions. For the installation, in cooperation with the municipal building department, the respective parking spaces had to be closed for traffic, signposted a few days in advance. Finally, the 10 sensors were installed in one day in the centre of Bolzano.

Although each individual position of the parking place sensors was checked for its suitability, technical problems occurred with signal strength during data transmission. After extensive further testing, an additional gateway antenna had to be installed in Bolzano and parking sensors had to be replaced and/or recalibrated. The search for the fault and the recalibration of the sensors installed in the asphalt took over two months and was only possible thanks to the good cooperation of all organisations involved.

It is intended in future to implement parking place sensors also in nature tourism areas, for example, at locations such as the GEOPARC Bletterbach. A GATE information flyer is planned for distribution via tourism associations to raise interest for the mobility solution for people with disabilities.

2.4.4 Potential for organisations

In the expansion of Smart City technology solutions in South Tyrol's municipalities reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities (and others spaces) can now be equipped with sensors for the "free/occupied" function. Smart City initiatives in other regions with a focus on applications for people with disabilities can benefit from the experiences in South Tyrol. But the technology for the "free/occupied" function can also be applied to other innovative mobility services such as charging stations for e-cars, bike sharing, and others.

2.4.5 The application in brief

Reserved parking spaces – free or occupied?

independent L. has developed a car park finder for people with disabilities as an inclusive application for barrier-free mobility in South Tyrol. The application covers 1.300 reserved parking spaces in the municipalities of South Tyrol, and comes with a notification function for users, accessibility description, adjustable font size, and text-to-speech function. Within the GATE project, the app for iOS and Android based devices was extended by the function "free/occupied", to display the occupancy status of the parking spaces in real time. In the pilot measure, also 10 parking spaces in Bolzano were equipped with an "in ground" parking space sensor. The sensor detects the presence or absence of a vehicle, and transmits the data in real time via LoRaWAN to the parking spaces database. Before the physical installation of sensors it is very important to test each position regarding the data transmission capability in order to prevent potential subsequent problems. The "free/occupied" functionality for the car park finder app has been developed by the software company U-Hopper, the databases and digital interfaces (web services) for the data transfer by independent L. For organisations interested to implement the solution in other regions of the Interreg programme information on the setup such as sensor, web services, etc. can be provided by independent L.